

Mini-Review

Are nucleic acid molecules ready to replace antibodies and enzymes in the diagnosis of infectious diseases?

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Introduction

Diagnosis of infectious diseases is a crucial step for accurate and timely treatment, prevention of further transmission, and disease management. Diagnostic tools and methods play an essential role in achieving diagnostic accuracy. There are multiple diagnostic tools available, each claiming varying sensitivity and specificity. However, rapid, easy-to-use, user-friendly, and cost-effective tools are always preferred for point-of-care (POC) applications. Proteins such as antibodies and enzymes have long been key components of rapid diagnostic tests. Over the decades, antigen/antibody-

based detection methods dominated the diagnostic field and market, particularly in rapid tests or ELISA formats. With the advances in biotechnology and interdisciplinary research, nucleic acids are emerging as promising detection agents for infectious diseases and various cancers. Consequently, detection methods are gradually shifting from traditional serum-derived antibodies to more ethical and serum-free biomolecules. Commercially used rapid tests and ELISA often rely on polyclonal or monoclonal antibodies derived from animals and usually contain serum components. Also, serum components may reduce the

specificity of these methods. Moreover, purification, storage, and transport at low temperature increases overall costs. At high temperatures, antibodies may lose sensitivity due to protein denaturation, and antibody detachment from indicator agents has been reported. In contrast, nucleic acids offer low-cost production and greater thermostability at a wide range of temperatures, making them more suitable for POC applications. Parallely, advances in microfluidics, 3D printing technologies, and interdisciplinary electrochemical approaches are providing innovative detection platforms. These innovations are enabling the design of novel diagnostic prototypes that can support healthcare systems in making timely and accurate diagnoses of infections and in managing disease without relying on expensive or sophisticated tools.

Aptamer-based detection

Aptamers are short nucleic acid molecules, either DNA or RNA, that are folded into specific three-dimensional structures enabling them to bind with a wide range of targets, including proteins,

inorganic ions, or nucleic acid. Due to their high specificity and affinity, aptamers emerge as promising detection agents for next-generation biosensors and rapid diagnostic devices. Along with the specificity offered by aptamers, they can be fabricated with advanced biomaterials and microfluidics to design sensitive, thermostable, compact, and portable diagnostic devices. The combination of microfluidics and aptamers has been explored in multiple prototype diagnostic platforms, including those based on lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) enzyme activity-based detection of malaria parasites. Two studies discussed here utilized the inherent enzymatic activity of *Plasmodium falciparum* lactate dehydrogenase (PfLDH) to enable sensitive detection of malaria parasites. With the aim of developing a multiplexed, high-sensitivity biosensor, Lewis A. Fraser et al. designed a microfluidic chamber containing immobilized aptamer-coated magnetic beads. The aptamers capture LDH from blood samples and generate a colorimetric signal upon the addition of substrate, which can be detected using a mobile device (Fraser et al., 2018).

Similarly, Adewoyin M. Ogunmolasuyi and coworkers developed a microfluidic paper-based analytical device (μ PAD) containing multiple zones (test zone 1, zone 3, and control zone 2). In this system, aptamers were immobilized using the biotin-streptavidin system. The immobilized aptamers selectively capture LDH from blood samples and produce a visible color signal, enabling equipment-free malaria detection (Ogunmolasuyi et al., 2022). Variations in aptamer binding affinity to their target biomarker may arise from several factors, including the immobilization strategy, the substrate or indicator reagent used, and the diagnostic platform employed (e.g., microfluidic chamber or paper-based device).

In viral infections, diagnostic tools often fail to detect viral DNA or RNA because measurable levels of viral nucleic acids may be absent or extremely low. These limitations necessitate the use of PCR amplification to generate a detectable number of copies of the target nucleic acid. However, despite amplification, the limit of detection is typically restricted to approximately 0.2-1 copies/ μ l. To achieve ultra-sensitive detection of viral DNA or

RNA without an amplification step and sophisticated equipment, Liqian Wang and colleagues introduced a molecular electromechanical biosensor integrated with field-effect transistors (FETs) (Wang et al., 2022). In this system, an aptamer probe is attached to a flexible single-stranded DNA and a rigid tetrahedral double-stranded DNA. Together, these components recognize specific ions or molecules, such as SARS-CoV-2 RNA, in the body fluid (nasopharyngeal swab in this study). Integration of this biomolecular assembly with electromechanical systems and FETs enables a sensitivity of 0.02 copies/ μ l for RNA load directly in the nasal swab samples. This molecular electromechanical system (MoEMS) significantly reduces the need for amplification steps and eliminates the need for sophisticated equipment such as thermal cyclers, while maintaining sensitivity comparable to amplification-based methods (Wang et al., 2022). Similarly, Seungwoo Song et al. suggested that aptamer-based sensors are well-suited to electrochemical detection systems. They demonstrated this by

fabricating peptide-aptamer-functionalized microneedles for cancer diagnosis, highlighting the potential of aptamer-integrated electrochemical platforms for sensitive biomarker detection (Song et al., 2019).

DNAzyme-based detection

DNAzyme is a functionalized nucleic acid (FNA) consisting of approximately 20-80 nucleotides that exhibits self-cleaving catalytic activity. FNAs can be either DNA or RNA enzymes, discovered in the 1980s as natural ribozymes and subsequently investigated to develop artificial FNAs for diverse applications. DNAzyme was first identified *in vitro* in 1994 by the Gerald F. Joyce group, and since then, its intrinsic RNA-cleaving catalytic activity has been widely explored for the detection of various metal ions, small molecules, and microorganisms. When combined with fluorophore and quencher, DNAzymes are developed to recognize various bacterial targets. Upon binding to a specific bacterium, DNAzymes cleave its RNA stretch, and the attached fluorophore is released from the quencher, generating a detectable fluorescent signal (Liu et al.,

2025). For example, M. Monsur Ali and colleagues reported that a DNAzyme-based biosensor can selectively detect *Klebsiella pneumoniae* on a paper-based substrate. In the presence of *K. pneumoniae*, DNAzyme cleaves off fluorescent DNA/RNA fragments, producing measurable fluorescent signals that enable real-time detection of *K. pneumoniae* infection. The study concluded with a sensitivity of 10^5 CFUs/mL (Ali et al., 2019). Similarly, Xia Zhong and coworkers designed a DNAzyme motor composed of target-activated DNAzyme nanowires and their corresponding substrates. In this system, both the DNAzyme and its substrate were co-immobilized on Au-Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles to reduce the distance between them, thereby enhancing the electrochemical signal response. This 3D design has significantly overcome the limitations associated with conventional DNAzyme-based biosensors, particularly those related to structural flexibility and low reactant concentration, thereby improving detection performance (Zhong et al., 2022).

Challenges and future aspects

Nucleic acids have demonstrated significant potential as molecular sensing element for diagnostic applications in recent years. Due to their flexible 3D structures, nucleic acids possess both structural binding capability and catalytic functionality, enabling the recognition of pathogens and their associated biomolecules. However, one of the major challenges in developing nucleic acid-based biosensors is the identification and screening of target-specific aptamers or DNAzymes. The systematic evolution of ligands by exponential enrichment (SELEX) process which involves multiple iterative rounds of selection and amplification, is commonly used to identify high-affinity aptamers. Additional rounds of SELEX enhance the screening of target-specific aptamers. To enhance the efficiency of aptamer selection, several modified SELEX methods has been developed, including capture-SELEX, microfluidic-SELEX, capillary electrophoresis SELEX (CE-SELEX), cell-SELEX, and microplate-SELEX. Despite

these advancements, many of these methods remain difficult to commercially scale and require skilled personnel to access quality control. Recently, artificial intelligence and *in silico* screening of aptamers made it possible to reduce time and resources by simply utilizing the crystal or modelled structure of the target. In contrast, the identification and large scale synthesis of catalytic DNAzymes as well as their integration with detection systems such as electrochemical or colorimetric platforms may compromise target specificity. Nevertheless, advances in bioengineering and nanobiotechnology have the potential to address these limitations and improve the performance of nucleic acid-based detection systems. Interdisciplinary integration of electrochemistry, microfluidics, and other emerging technologies may further accelerate the development of robust and highly sensitive nucleic acid-based biosensors (Liu et al., 2025).

Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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